

Worldwide efforts for the ILC

IDT-WG2
Shin MICHIZONO

- Americas
- CERN
- France
- Germany
- Italy
- Spain
- UK

資料については、Sergey Belomestnykh（米国フェルミ研究所）、Philip Burrows（英国オックスフォード大学）、Enrico Cenni（フランスCEA）、Angeles Faus-Golfe（フランスIJClab）、Bob Laxdal（カナダTRIUMF）、Laura Monaco（イタリアINFN）、Hans Weise（ドイツDESY）、Juan Fuster（スペインIFIC）、Steinar Stapnes（CERN）に協力いただいた。

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IDT-WG2

IDT-WG2 has about 50 accelerator researchers from around the world participating in discussions on ILC accelerator development research.

ILCに関連する国際的な取り組みの例

	～2017	2018～2021
CERN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ATFでのナノビーム協力 SRF空洞・クライオモジュール工業化検討 冷凍機・ビームダンプ・土木設計協力 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ATFでのナノビーム協力、SRF空洞製造技術、冷凍機・ビームダンプ・土木設計協力 ヨーロッパのILC研究開発全体取り纏め
アメリカ地域 (アメリカ、カナダ)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LCLS-II 建設 LCLS-II用の新SRF空洞処理方法の開発 HL-LHC用クラブ空洞開発 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SRF空洞、高性能化・コスト削減の日米協力 LCLS-II用クライオモジュールの技術開発、建設 米・カナダによるHL-LHC用クラブ空洞の物納貢献
フランス	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 欧州XFELでのSRF入力カプラー、モジュールの組立て実績 ATFでのナノビーム協力 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 欧州中性子源(ESS)、米国PIP-IIプロジェクトへの物納貢献 SRFの空洞高性能化。ATFナノビーム協力
ドイツ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TESLA計画(ILCの前進)の推進 2007から欧州XFELの建設 TDRのSRFコスト見積もり 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 欧州XFELの安定運転による大型SRF加速器の実証 SRF空洞高性能化
イタリア	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 空洞、クライオモジュール、チューナー設計(TDR) 欧州XFELでの空洞・クライオモジュールの半数製造 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 欧州中性子源(ESS)、米国PIP-IIプロジェクトへの物納貢献 ドイツのBESSY storage ringの空洞チューナー設計
スペイン	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ATFでのナノビーム協力 欧州XFELの超伝導電磁石など物納貢献 日本のIFMIF(六ヶ所)への物納貢献 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 欧州中性子源(ESS)への物納貢献 ILC超伝導マグネット技術開発(予算獲得)
イギリス	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ATFナノビーム協力、ダンピングリング 陽電子源、ビーム伝送、高周波源、ビームダンプのTDRへの貢献 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 欧州中性子源(ESS)、米国PIP-IIプロジェクトへの物納貢献 LHCクラブ空洞の設計、技術開発

Worldwide efforts for the ILC

	~2017	2018~2021
CERN	Cooperation on nano-beam at ATF, study on industrialization of cavity and cryomodule for SRF, cooperation on design of cryogenics, beam dump, and civil engineering	Nanobeam collaboration at ATF, SRF cavity fabrication technology, cryogenics, beam dump and civil design collaboration. Overall coordination of ILC R&D in Europe.
Americas (USA+Canada)	Start of construction of LCLS-II; development of a new SRF cavity treatment method for LCLS-II; development of a crab cavity for HL-LHC.	US-Japan collaboration on SRF cavity performance improvement and cost reduction, assembly and installation of cryomodules for LCLS-II . Production began for in-kind contributions of the RFD crab cavities and cryomodules to the HL-LHC by the US & Canada
France	Experience in assembly of SRF input couplers and cryomodule assembly at XFEL in Europe, cooperation with Nanobeam at ATF	In-kind contributions to the European Neutron Source (ESS), the US PIP-II project, cavity performance improvement at SRF, nanobeam collaboration at ATF.
Germany	TESLA (preliminary stage of ILC) planning study, XFEL construction started in 2007, SRF cost estimate for TDR.	Demonstration of large SRF accelerator with stable operation of XFEL, and improvement of SRF cavity performance
Italy	Contribution to ILC-TDR for cryomodules, cavities and reference Blade tuners, in-kind contribution to half of the cavities and cryomodules at XFEL in Europe.	In-kind contributions to the European Neutron Source (ESS), the US PIP-II project, cavity tuner design at the VSR Upgrade of BESSY storage ring HZB
Spain	Nanobeam collaboration at ATF, in-kind contributions such as superconducting magnets at European XFEL, in-kind contributions to IFMIF in Japan	In-Kind contribution to the European Neutron Source (ESS), CIEMAT was awarded a budget for the R&D of the ILC superconducting magnet.
UK	Nanobeam collaboration at ATF. Contributions to TDR for damping rings, positron sources, beam delivery system, RF sources, and beam dump.	In-kind contributions to the European Neutron Source (ESS) and the US PIP-II projects, design of the LHC crab cavity.

Americas

(USA + Canada)

USA + Canada

SRF (ANL, Cornell University, FNAL, JLab, Old Dominion University, SLAC)

up to 2018

- Participated in the International collaborative cavity performance evaluation test at S1 Global, incorporating Japanese, European, and US cavities, in 2010.
- Construction of the Fermilab Accelerator Science and Technology (FAST) facility based on the ILC SRF technology in 2015. Demonstrated operation of the ILC-type cryomodule (CM) at an average gradient of 31.5 MV/m, accelerating bunches with ILC parameters.
- After discovery of the nitrogen doping at Fermilab, developed a recipe for LCLS-II SRF linac – a collaborative effort of Fermilab, JLab, Cornell, and SLAC.
- Beginning of the LCLS-II cryomodule production at Fermilab and JLab.
- Developed novel crab cavity designs for HL-LHC: Double Quarter Wave (DQW) by BNL/CERN and RadioFrequency Dipole (RFD) by ODU/SLAC/JLab. Developed a novel QMiR crab cavity design for the SPX experiment at ANL by FNAL/ANL.

2018 – 2021

- Work on cost reduction and performance improvement of superconducting cavities through international cooperation (Japan/U.S.) – several R&D efforts at Fermilab, JLab and Cornell.
- Under the ILC cost reduction program, Fermilab discovered new SRF cavity treatments for high field, low-loss operation, such as nitrogen infusion and two-step baking. These recipes are also being applied and tested at KEK and other U.S. and European labs.
- Began construction of a High Gradient CryoModule (HGCM) with a goal to demonstrate operation at >38 MV/m.
- Completed LCLS-II cryomodule production (~40 CM) with excellent results exceeding specifications – 157 MeV energy gain per CM (128 MeV spec) and $Q = 3.1 \times 10^{10}$ (2.7×10^{10} spec) – Fermilab and JLab.
- Developed new, improved nitrogen doping recipes for LCLS-II-HE (Fermilab and JLab).
- Began production of the LCLS-II-HE cryomodules (~20 cryomodules) using FNAL's nitrogen doping recipe.
- Began production of the RFD crab cavities as part of the U.S. HL-LHC Accelerator Upgrade Project (AUP) – Fermilab (lead institution), ANL, ODU/JLab. Began facility design and preparations for the RFD crab cavity cryomodule assembly and testing at TRIUMF (Canada) in collaboration with CERN, UK and USA. The crab cavity development for the HL-LHC is a prime example of a successful international collaboration in developing accelerator systems
- Proposed and began R&D on 3 crab cavity designs, to be down-selected in 2022.

Final Focus doublet magnet (BNL)

up to 2018

- Baseline design uses actively shielded QD0 produced via BNL Direct Wind technology. The QD0 vibration test was planned (an important test to address the Final Focus vibration stability.) BNL has manufactured most of the parts needed for the test.

2018 – 2021

- BNL Direct Wind technology was greatly advanced (examples: Double Helical coil winding for EIC and FCC-ee IRs and the Sweet Spot coil concept for EIC.)

Damping Ring (Cornell University)

up to 2018

- Damping ring lattice, layout and components.

2018 – 2021

- Measurement, modeling and analysis of electron cloud effects

SRF technology development at US institutions

FAST SRF linac (one ILC-type CM)

SRF cavity with T-map at Cornell

LCLS-II CM in a test facility at FNAL

Rotational BCP tool for RFD cavity at ANL/FNAL facility

End of day
05 Oct 2020

LCLS-II-HE cavities assembled into a cavity string

RF Dipole crab cavity (ODU)

Vertical Test Facility at FNAL

Quasi-Waveguide Multicell Deflecting Resonator (QMIR)

SRF activity in 2018-2021 (WP-1)

R&D on new surface treatments for high Q and high gradients

ILC Cost Reduction R&D global effort explores doping parameter space to extend high Q at the highest gradients

Comparison of the standard ILC recipe (1DE3) with two-step baked SRF cavities

High gradient cryomodule demonstration

- Fermilab is in the process of preparing a CM to demonstrate the new SRF advances
- Supported by the ILC Cost Reduction R&D with contributions from other labs throughout the world
- Gradient goal: 38 MV/m average gradient with a stretch goal of 40 MV/m. Q_0 goal: 1.0×10^{10} at 38 MV/m.

Cavity candidates (average gradient 41 MV/m):

- TB9AES011 – 41.3 MV/m
- TB9ACC011 – 45.5 MV/m
- TB9ACC012 – 36.9 MV/m
- TB9ACC013 – 40.4 MV/m

SRF activity in 2018-2021 (WP-2)

Updating the ILC cryomodule design

Tuner that satisfied all specs for ILC already exist ...
FNAL designed LCLS II TUNER

- ✓ Compact double-lever Tuner that fit on the "short-short" cavity.
- ✓ Robust/Low cost tuner frame design.
- ✓ High tuner stiffness for minimization of LFD
- ✓ Tuner design allow to replace actuators (stepper & piezo) through designated CM port without tuner dis-assembly
- ✓ Slow tuner range more than 800kHz
- ✓ Encapsulated piezo actuators translated stroke directly to the cavity (piezo stroke >2,5kHz and low group delay- important for active LFD compensation)
- ✓ More than 300 tuners that built and deployed at 40 LCLS II have been cold tested/qualified for LINAC operations

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Yury Pischaikov, SRF Cavity Tuners AN/NC2020

Fermilab

- High-pressure-gas safety regulations: **Globally Harmonized HPG Safety Guidelines** need to be established for ILC SRF Cavity/Cryomodule design and production during the ILC Pre-Lab phase. This work is led by KEK in close collaboration with FNAL and other institutions.
- Incorporating lessons learned from European XFEL and LCLS-II production.
- Some component designs are re-evaluated, and a particular design selected. E.g., LCLS-II tuner might be a very good option for ILC.

Future SRF plan in the USA (WP-1 and WP-2)

The U.S. national labs and universities have established expertise, track record, and advanced SRF technological capabilities to contribute to WP-1, WP-2 and WP-3.

WP-2

WP-1

40 cavity production

ILC cavity with blade tuner (TDR)

LCLS-II tuner (update)

One CM from the U.S.A. to be transported for performance test at KEK

Cavity production readiness includes

- cavities with He tank & magnetic shield around the cavity
- high-pressure-gas regulation
- surface preparation / heat treatment
- vertical test

Establish requirements for Nb material, and recipe for surface treatment

Cavity production success yield to be confirmed

SRF activity in 2018-2021 & forthcoming plans (WP-3)

- There are significant crab cavity (CC) developments since ILC TDR in 2013. Several potential new solutions for ILC CC include designs developed in the USA:
 - DQW for EIC and HL-LHC – BNL/CERN
 - RFD for EIC, HL-LHC, other projects – ODU/JLab/SLAC
 - QMiR for SPX at ANL and ELETTRA – FNAL/ANL
- A design will be down-selected during Pre-Lab

Final Focus magnet development at BNL

ILC FF magnet TDR design

ILC Requirement is 50 nm QD0 vibrational stability!
 1.9 K pressurized superfluid helium cooling is used in order not to have “flowing cryogens” (avoid vibrations).

ILC QD0

The ILC QD0 R&D magnet prototype cryostat is 90% complete and almost ready for insertion of the magnet coils on the “sled assembly.”

Activity in 2018-2021

QC1 Local Field Tailoring

EIC Sweet Spot Coil Example

Future FF QD0 plan in the USA (WP-16)

WP16 Task #1: Complete QD0 Prototype Vibration Testing

- Concept: Measure magnetic center movement via multiturn pickup coil and cross check against internal/external geophones and laser doppler vibrometer looking at cold mass inside the main cryostat.
- Will take advantage of the US/Japan program SuperKEKB developments.

WP16 Task #2: Improve the ILC Final Focus Magnet Design

- Re-optimize the IR magnet coil parameters (the ILC TDR IR baseline was optimized for 500 GeV CM energy) and utilize the latest advances in the BNL Direct Wind technology.
- Formulate detector specific anti-solenoid configurations and confirm that these designs satisfy ILC FF optics and MDI requirements.
- There is a possibility to reduce the transverse size of the QD0 cryostat in the detectors (MDI desirable) by taking advantage of recent developments: tapered coils are used for some of the EIC low- β quads that are closest to the IP (Q1APR/Q1ER). To fit inside limited space, Double Helical coils are used.

Tapered Quadrupole for EIC FF

Compact Force-Neutral Anti-Solenoid

Damping ring development at Cornell

Damping ring lattice and layout

Low emittance tuning algorithm and magnet alignment and BPM resolution specifications

Achieves $< 1\text{pm}$ in 3 iterations

Superconducting
Damping Wiggler Design

Ring components

Damping Wiggler Vacuum chambers
with e-cloud mitigation

Damping ring activity in 2018-2021

Electron cloud simulation tools

Detailed simulation of photon trajectories and scattering for modeling electron cloud effects

Photon trajectories without grooves on the chamber walls

Photon trajectories with grooves

Measurement of electron cloud induced tune shifts

Vertical(top) and horizontal (bottom) tune shifts for a 30-bunch train with trailing witness bunches of various current. *Witness bunch tune shifts are nearly independent of bunch charge.*

Modeling of electron cloud tune shifts and comparison with measurements

Measured (black points) and modeled tune shifts for a 30-bunch train of positrons, horizontal at left and vertical at right. Contribution from the field free regions of the ring are shown in blue, dipole regions in green and the sum of the two in red.

The top row (0.4 mA/b) \Leftrightarrow 0.64 E10 positrons/bunch
 Bottom row (0.7 mA/b) \Leftrightarrow 1.12 E10 positrons/bunch

CERN

CERN's Activities for ILC Acc. Technology

~ 2017

- **Nano-beam: Achieved** the Final Focus beam size of 41 nm at ATF-II, equivalent to 7 nm at ILC-FF.
- **SRF:** Progressed industrialization study of cavity and cryomodule fabrication,
- **RF:** Developed fundamental input-coupler w/ new-ceramic,
- **Cryogenics:** Progressed the system design reliable & sustainable in emergency, total power failure,
- **Beam Dump:** Investigated > 10 MW water-dump design feasibility,
- **Civil Engineering:** Developed Tunnel Optimization Tool (TOT), referring the FCC CE study at CERN,

2018 ~ 2021

- **Nano-beam:** demonstrated the stability, focusing on beam dynamics, wake field, and ground vibration,
- **SRF:** developed new fabrication technology (such as inner-EB welding and hydroforming),
- **RF:** Developed high-efficiency RF source (klystron) with applying superconducting magnet technology,
- **Cryogenics:** Established the sustainable system-design to conserve helium resource in any emergencies,
- **Beam dump,** Developed remote-handling technology in particular for beam-window maintenance,
- **Civil engineering** design, reflecting CERN's HL-LHC civil work for vertical shafts at beam interaction points.

Plan (2022 ~ : Pre-Lab)

- **Lead European Cooperation** for ILC-Pre-Lab
- Nano-beam: Contribution to the ATF2/ATF3 program,
- SRF, RF, Cryog., Beam Dump, Beam Dynamics,

Progress in FF Beam Size and Stability at ATF2

Goal 1: Establish the ILC final focus method with same optics and comparable beamline tolerances

- ATF2 Goal : **37 nm** → ILC **6 nm**
- Achieved 41 nm (2016)**

Goal 2: Develop a few nm position stabilization for the ILC collision

- FB latency 133 nsec achieved** (target: < 300 nsec)
- positon jitter at IP: 106 → 41 nm (2018)** (limited by the BPM resolution)

Nano-meter stabilization at IP (2018)

CERN's Activity for Nano-beam at ATF2

■ Nanometer Beam Development

- **Final Focus System studies for LCs**
Wakefield free steering method lead by CERN.

■ Ground Motion Feed-forward for CLIC

14 Geophones has been installed in ATF2 by CERN and LAPP

- **Ultra Low-beta optics for CLIC**
Two Octupoles by CERN has been installed.

OCTU1 installed in ATF

■ Beam Monitor Developments

High resolution OTR-ODR, ChDR monitor

Collaborative Research Contract between CERN and KEK supports the ATF beam operation.

CERN-KEK Cooperation on SRF Cavity Technology

Inner-EB welding & Coupler with new Ceramic Window

- ◆ Coating-free ceramic w/ low secondary electron emission,

Auto-conditioning Module by CERN

Good collaboration between CERN and KEK
(Thank you very much)

Courtesy of Charles Jolic

We connected RF_{in}, RF_{out} and Vacuum output (only one ch.) to this module.

CERN contributions to coupler RF test-stand, picture)

SCRF studies at CERN in contact with ILC Collaboration on “inside” EB welding for cavities (fabrication techniques)

ILC Cryogenics Configuration, referring CERN-LHC

CERN-LHC Cryogenics (network) configuration is an important reference for the ILC

ILC Beam Dump Design of 18 MW with common features with CLIC

CERN-LHC Beam Dump

Common Mountainous Condition in FCC and ILC

Tunnel Optimization Tool (TOT), originally developed for FCC study, contributing to cost-effective ILC Civil Engineering study

TOT may find optimum CE layout and access tunnel locations

LC studies at CERN in 2021-25

CLIC and High Gradient technology:

- Design and manufacturing of X-band structures and components, system interfaces
- Study structures breakdown limits and optimization, operation and conditioning
- Beam-dynamics and parameters: Nanobeams (focus on beam-delivery), pushing multi-TeV region (parameters and beam structure vs energy efficiency)
- Tests in CLEAR (wakefields, instrumentation) and other facilities (e.g. ATF2)

Application of X-band technology (examples):

- A compact FEL (CompactLight: EU Design Study 2018-21)
- Compact Medical linacs (proton and electrons)
- Inverse Compton Scattering Source (Smart-Light)
- Linearizers and deflectors in FELs (PSI, DESY, more)
- 1 GeV X-band linac at LNF

ILC related R&D and Pre-lab Planning

- Positron flux concentrator, ATF2/3, Hi-klystrons, various SRF topics, cryo, dumps, beam-dynamics, DR, etc
- IDT participation and Common Fund contributions.
- Numerous ILC and/or KEK collaborative R&Ds, linking to CLIC, generic R&D or SRF for HL LHC and FCC and other CERN activities.

R&D Area With Common Interests

Topics	CLIC – ILC communality	Other	Status wrt ILC and KEK
CE and Cryo	CE common	LHC, all future project	WG2 reps from CERN
ATF2(3), BDS, beamdynamics, instrumentation and related beam-elements	Common	Other nanobeam projects	Participate in ATF3 study – BDS optimization, WG2 rep. from CERN
Positrons	Common for e-driven	All e+e- colliders	WG2 rep. from CERN, target, AMD, pulsed magnet for undulator version
Damping Rings	Common	All low emittance rings	Possible effort (performance studies, design and also kicker for CLIC relevant) – only partly in current LC studies, WG2 rep. from CERN
Hi-Eff klystron	Common (L-band)	FCC, CEPC etc	Designed (also ongoing SC solenoid work with KEK), now in Hi-Eff klystron project
SCRF cavities	For ILC	SCRF generally	Common manufacture studies, e.g. internal EB welding studies/hydro-forming, long term Nb3Sn studies, surface treatment, crab-cavities, WG2 rep. from CERN, recent APT first attempt to include limited personnel in this area
Couplers	For ILC	SCRF generally	Possible design effort, also common work in the past
Beam dumps	Common	(HL)LHC/FCC/muons ..	Advisory, visits and common studies to be considered
Physics and Detectors	Common	Higgs factories	Some common tools, not defined longer term
CERN – KEK office, agreements, WEB pages, LCWS	Partly common	NA	LC project office at CERN working with KEK communication and international office

France

SRF: ~2017

- Construction of SUPRATECH, a research platform dedicated to R&D on SRF, operational since 2006 (IJClab)
- Construction of SRF High Power Coupler (HPC) laboratory dedicated to the conditioning and quality test of SRF power couplers (assembly clean room, baking oven, 5MW power test), operational since 2013 (IJClab)
- Construction of the vacuum and surfaces platform dedicated to the: surface analysis, thin film coating deposition, stimulated desorption measurements and investigation of secondary particles emitted from a surface subjected to a particle bombardment; creation in 2014 (IJCLab)
- Construction of the Analysis and Control of vibration Platform, operational since ~2010 (LAPP)
- Construction of a Multipacting analysis laboratory (localization and testing), operational since 2019 (LPSC)
- Participation in the SPIRAL2 project at GANIL with, among other things, the design, fabrication, assembly, test and commissioning of 7 QWR cryomodules (cavities, power couplers and cold tuning system), and of the Cryogenic Distribution System of the whole SRF linac (2005–2019) (IJClab, LPSC, GANIL)
- Participation in the XFEL project at DESY with the conditioning and quality test of 670 (RI) + 150 (CPI) High Power Couplers (8–12 HPCs per week) (2013– 2016) (IJClab)

2018~2021

- Participation in the ESS project with the fabrication, assembly and test of 13 (+1) Spoke cryomodules (cavities, power couplers and cold tuning system), Full Cryogenic Distribution System (CDS) for the spoke section (valve boxes and header units) (2014–2022) (IJClab)
- Participation in the ADS MYRRHA design and construction phases at SCK–CEN (Belgium) with, among several other things, the design and prototyping of the Spoke SRF section “elementary brick” (fully equipped cryomodule and cryogenic system) (2011–2026) (IJClab, LPSC, IPHC).
- Participation in PIP-II development at Fermilab: prototyping of cryomodule components (4 Single Spoke Resonator (SSR2) cavities, 5 SSR2 cold tuners, 4 SRR high power couplers) (2020–2022) and support for the production phase of 33 SSR2 (6 CMs + 3 yield) (validation in vertical cryostat, surface reprocessing and shipping) (2022–2026) (IJClab).
- R&D on SRF: Heat-treatments (infusion tests) and diagnostic of Nb cavities, alternative fabrication procedures and SC materials studies (thin film), mitigation of multipacting, optimization on SRF ancillaries (couplers, tuners) and LLRF.

Nano-beams

~2017

- Participation in the Nanobeam Test Facility (ATF2) R&D program: Development of tuning techniques, emittance growth studies, Origin, control and measurement of the halo (diamond detectors and collimator), construction of the IPBPM (support and chamber) (IJClab), control and mitigation of beam vibrations by means of Active Vibration Controls (LAPP)

2018~2021

- R&D on intensity dependence and wakefield mitigation to reduce beam performance degradation on ILC (IJClab)
- R&D on ultra-low beam sizes and related correcting high-order aberrations in ATF2 (IJClab)
- R&D on the vibration for the final doublet in ATF2 (IJClab)
- Participation in the ATF review of the experimental results and future plans at ATF to date in 2020

Positrons

~2017

- R&D of unpolarised positron sources more specifically the so-called hybrid positron source, based on channeling radiation.

2018~2021

- R&D of unpolarised positron sources more specifically the so-called hybrid positron source, based on channeling radiation. New series of experimental data taking in SuperKEKB to test this new technique in 2018.

Polarimetry

~2017

- Participation in the Advanced Technology Facility (ATF) R&D program: pulsed laser Compton scattering experiment to produce gamma rays on ATF Damping Ring (IJClab)
- R&D on Compton Polarimeter for ILC based in the HERA Compton polarimeter experience, where a relative few per mille precision were obtained (IJClab)

SRF activities at IN2P3 (1)

Power coupler activity at IN2P3 - IJCLab

Section of the European XFEL High Power Coupler model, main parts are the cold part, warm part, warm transition and tuning motor

RF conditioning automated procedure for 4 parallel test stands

Power couplers mass production for Eu-XFEL (808 units)

SRF activities at IN2P3 (2)

SUPRATECH platform at IN2P3 - IJCLab

Vacuum furnace

ISO 4 clean room

Cryogenic test hall for cryomodules

Assembly hall

Chemical etching lab (BCP only)

Helium liquefier

Vertical cryostat

+ Material science lab

PLATEFORME D'ANALYSE
PANAMA
Ile de France

- GXRD
- SIMS
- Confocal microscope
- SEM (EDS, EBSD)
- SEY measurement

+ Other

- RRR measurement (Supratech)
- Conductivity (Supratech)
- TEM (Jannus Platform)

SRF activities at IN2P3 (3)

ESS activities at IJClab

CM assembly

The 13 (+1) spoke cryomodules composing the first superconducting acceleration stage of ESS.

The full cryogenic distribution system for the spoke section (13 valve boxes, cryolines, cryo end box)

Valve boxes during test

Header units during assembly

Activities at IN2P3 (4)

Nanobeams activities at IN2P3

IPBPM system at ATF2

Halo studies and collimation at ATF2

Active Vibration Control at ATF2

Positron activities at IN2P3

Positron production at SuperKEKB

Replace the compact (bulk) target-converter by a granular one made of small spheres

Granular targets for the experiment:

Hybrid scheme for e+ production

Granular target-converter can provide **better heat dissipation** associated with the ratio Surface/Volume of the spheres and the **better resistance to the shocks**.

Activities at IN2P3 (5)

Polarimetry activities at IN2P3

Compton Polarimeter for ILC

SRF activities at IN2P3 (2018-2021) (1)

IN2P2 contribution to MYRRHA

Elementary brick

Vertical tests of the Spoke cavities

Test at 300K of the tuning system

Power coupler

IN2P3 CONTRIBUTION TO PIP-II

PROTOTYPING PHASE (2020 – 2022)

PRODUCTION PHASE (2022 – 2026)

Activities at IN2P3 (2018-2021) (2)

IN2P2 contribution to ATF2 goals

Nanobeam sizes

ATF2 goals

Goal 1: Establish the ILC final focus method with same optics and comparable beamline tolerances

• ATF2 Goal: 37 nm → ILC 7.7 nm (ILC250)

• Achieved 41 nm (2016)

Goal 2: Develop a few nm position stabilization for the ILC collision

• FB latency 133 nsec achieved (target: < 366 nsec)

• position jitter at IP: 106 → 41 nm (2018) (limited by the BPM resolution)

But small beam sizes were obtained with beam intensities of $0.5\text{-}1.5 \cdot 10^9 \text{ e}^-/\text{bunch}$ (10^{10} design value)

Beam size shows a degradation with increase of the intensity compatible with wakefields

ATF2 wakefield knobs system between BPM QD10BFF and QD10AFF

- Ultra-low b_y^* and high-order aberrations studies
- Wakefield evaluation and mitigation
- Vibrations long-term monitoring system

Intensity dependence studies

ILC-IDT 2020

Ultra low β^* studies

8 December 2020

Instrumentation R&D

Incoherent Diffraction Cherenkov Radiation (ICDR)

Nanobeam stabilization

Coherence study at ATF2

Future IN2P3 plan at IN2P3(WP-1/2)

IN2P3 has advanced technological capabilities in SRF and has the ability to contribute to WP-1 and WP-2.

WP-1

40 cavity production

Nb material

electropolishing

Heat treatment

Confirm ILC recipe

Future IN2P3 plan at IN2P3(WP-8/9/10/15/16)

IN2P3 has advanced technological capabilities in SRF and has the ability to contribute to WP8-9-10, WP-15 and WP-16.

WP-8/9/10

e-driven ILC positron source

Target cross section

Flux concentrator design

Field map of APS cavity calculated by Superfish.

WP-15

ILC FFS - ATF3 objective and collaboration:

Based on the achievements of the ATF2, ATF3 plan is to pursue the necessary R&D to maximize the luminosity potential of ILC. In particular the assessment of the ILC FFS system design from the point of view of the beam dynamics aspects and the technological/hardware choices and the long-term stability operation issues.

WP-16

QD0 active shielding coils layout

Example of ILC 250 QD0 cryostat using shorter QD0 SC coils ($L^* = 4.1$ m)

Baseline half-length QD0 Direct Wind R&D coil layer production

BNL Direct Wind constant gradient tapered double helical coil winding

Until 2018:

- SOLEIL (storage ring RF cavity and 3rd harmonic design and assembly)
- SPIRAL2 (12 cryomodules, cavities and main coupler design and assembly)
- XFEL (103 cryomodules assembly)
- IFMIF (design and assembly of cryomodule, cavities and main coupler)
- ESS (medium and high beta cavities and main coupler design and prototyping)
- SARAF (cryomodule, cavities and main coupler design and prototyping)

After 2018:

- ESS (32 cryomodule assembly, 120 main coupler series and cryomodule testing)
- SARAF (4 cryomodule assembly and testing)
- PIPII (10 cryomodule assembly and testing)

R&D related to ILC:

- Japan/Europe cost reduction effort
- Vertical electro polishing study (collaboration with KEK and Marui Galvanizing Co. Ltd)
- Cavities preparation and testing
- High gradient cryomodule project (collaboration with Fermilab and KEK), cavity preparation, magnetic shield development and assembly robotization
- Clean room robotization development

ESS: cavity and coupler design, procurement of all components but cavities, integration of 32 cryomodules

SPIRAL2: design and assembly of 12 cryomodules

XFEL: assembly of 103 cryomodules (1 CM/4 days)

XFEL Village

- XFEL village (1350m²)
- Throughput (1 cryomodule/4 days)
- 52 cryomodules/year (1 shift only!)
- 103 cryomodules delivered (10% of ILC)

CEA has a long experience in SRF technology and can contribute to **WP-1** and **WP-2**:

- Cavity preparation recipe and industrialization R&D
- Cryomodule assembly
- Clean room robotization development

Germany

Germany: Summary

- ~2017: E-XFEL construction and completion
 - 1992 TESLA (TeV-Energy Superconducting Linear Accelerator) was established as ILC prototype
 - 1999 TTF (TESLA Test Facility) was constructed (later known as FLASH)
 - 2001 TESLA proposal submitted
 - 2007 Euro-XFEL construction started, beam operation for users started from 2017
- 2018~2021: E-XFEL operation and High-Q/High-G R&D started
 - Euro-XFEL has been operated stably with higher reliability for users
 - R&D for CW operation as Euro-XFEL upgrade plan started
 - High-Q/High-G R&D started by collaboration with EU-JP-US (with U. Hamburg)
- 2022~: Upgrading for CW operation at E-XFEL and High-Q/High-G R&D continued
 - R&D for CW operation at Euro-XFEL
 - New vacuum furnace will be introduced for 1-cell
 - High-Q/High-G R&D will be continued (with U. Hamburg)

※TESLA Technology Collaboration Meeting is regularly held every year, to present research activity and exchange information among labs

~ 2017: E-XFEL construction and completion

Beam operation started from 2017 at DESY in Hamburg/Germany
At present, it's the longest SRF linac in the world (~1/10 scale as ILC)
800 cavities and 100 Cryomodules are used

Parts were procured internationally and manufactured and assembled in Europe

3 km as total length
(2 km as SRF linac)

Experimental Hall

Main Linac

Injector

~ 2017: E-XFEL construction and completion

Performance tests for cavity and CM were done at DESY.

At its peak, eight cavity tests were performed every week, and one CM test was performed every week. The CM test was stopped administratively at 31 MV/m. The test pits are 4 cavities x 2 pits and 1 CM x 3 pits.

RI results only (ILC recipe)

First-pass	Yield >28 MV/m Average >28 MV/m
First+Second pass	Yield >28 MV/m Average >28 MV/m
First+Second+third pass	Yield >28 MV/m Average >28 MV/m

“Usable” means Q_0 and X-rays spec. are also satisfied

ILC TDR (assumed)	XFEL	
	max	usable
75%	85%	63%
35 MV/m	35.2 MV/m	33.5 MV/m
90%	94%	82%
35 MV/m	35.0 MV/m	33.4 MV/m
-	-	91%
-	-	33.4 MV/m

Since the Eu-XFEL surface treatment process is not identical to that of ILC, simple comparison is difficult, but the ILC requirements are almost achieved.

2018~2021: E-XFEL operation

E-XFEL, started operation in 2017, has been steadily increasing its energy and reached its goal in 2018. Currently, the E-XFEL is running user operation stably. The cryogenics system (compressor) is controlled to keep the dynamic heat load for stable operation.

SRF Operation at XFEL: Lessons Learned After More Than One Year

Denis Koehn, May 20th, 2019

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Tuning for RF power distribution was done by MGTf for energy increase

When RF off, the heater is turned on to keep the dynamic heat load

- Avoid disturbance induced by RF changes
- Quenches
- Sudden massive gradient changes
- Dynamic heat load fluctuations compensated by heaters

Stable He level and pressure

Pdiss computation based on RF gradient, flat top duration, and quench alarms

Julien Branlard, TTC, 21.01.2021

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Heater compensation 48

2018~2021: High-Q/High-G R&D started

High-Q/High-G R&D is being carried out in collaboration with DESY and the U. Hamburg. A new heat treatment has been tried using the existing vacuum furnace, but no good results have been obtained so far. Sample tests are being conducted at the same time.

Infusion recipe:

2022 ~ : E-XFEL upgrade and High-Q/High-G R&D continued

E-XFEL is currently studying a plan to optimize the upstream CMs to CW, and is developing the necessary technology for this purpose. On the other hand, for High-Q/High-G R&D, a new vacuum furnace will be installed in collaboration with U. Hamburg, and R&D using a single cell cavity will be promoted.

Possible CW Upgrade

- Continuous Wave (CW) mode is the origin of the SRF accelerator technology. Eu-XFEL project was based on the Linear Collider (LC) technology (TESLA) operating in the pulsed RF power mode (10 Hz / 650 μ s beam pulse). Many FEL user experiments will get an advantage (or become possible) with CW mode operation.
- Possible beam parameters: 25 μ A (100 pC and 250 kHz) with 8 GeV (CW) and 12 GeV (long-pulse: \sim 100ms).
- Several CMs were successfully tested in CW and long-pulse mode in CMTB at DESY.

The Upgrade Plan:

- Replace the front-end cryomodules (17x)
 - Larger cooling capability
 - CW optimized cavities
- Install CW capable RF sources
 - 1 \times IOT per RF station
- Double the cryo plant (cost driver)
 - 2.5 \rightarrow 5kW
- CW electron gun (preferred option: SRF gun).
- The former front-end cryomodules can be installed at the end of the linac to lengthen L3 (+4 RF stations), no further action required in L3 ($>$ 1km).
- The upgraded XFEL would be capable of short pulse, long pulse AND CW operation.

Italy

INFN Italy:

~ 2017:

- **LEP-2:** collaboration with CERN for industrialization and production in Italy of 1/3 of the SRF cavities.
- **TESLA collaboration:** photocathodes for high brightness injectors, cryomodule design cold mass and WPMs, Tuners (FLASH, VUV-FEL), TESLA TDR.
- **TRASCO/PDS-XDS/EUROTRANS/MAX:** 704 MHz $\beta = 0.47$ cavities produced (RF and mechanical design, construction), vertically tested at LASA, dressed (blade tuner, magnetic shield) and integrated in a horizontal test module at IPM-Orsay.
- **SNS:** EM design of 800 MHz SRF cavities ($\beta = 0.61$ & $\beta = 0.81$).
- **CM2 Module for FNAL ILC-TA:** type-III cold mass and Blade tuners for the short version of the 1.3 GHz TESLA cavities.
- **ILC S1-Global:** realization of a plug-compatibility test module containing components from different partners (FNAL/DESY/INFN).
- **ILC TDR:** contribution to TDR for cryomodules, cavities and reference Blade tuners.
- **E-XFEL:** in-kind contribution for the production of half of the 1.3 GHz cavities and cryomodules, design and delivery of the 3.9 GHz complete cryomodule plus one complete spare (2 x eight 9-cell cavities, blade tuners, magnetic shields, cold masses, cryomodules, etc.), co-WP leader for production and qualification of 800 fast tuners.

2018 ~ 2021:

- **ESS:** in-kind contribution of 36 704.4 MHz SRF cavities for the medium beta section ($\beta = 0.67$). RF and mechanical design, definition and optimization of treatment and production cycle, prototype and series production. Development of new rotational BCP, optimization of the HPR geometry.
- **PIP-II:** in-kind contribution of 38 650 MHz SRF cavities for the low beta section ($\beta = 0.61$). RF and mechanical design, treatments, production cycle and qualification of prototypes (five 1-cell and two 5-cells cavities). Series cavities: started procurement of Nb and preparation of remaining main call for tenders. R&D on treatments (EP, annealing, mid T baking, doping, etc.) for the High-Q performance.
- **VSR Upgrade of BESSY storage ring HZB:** design and qualification of a novel coaxial tuner for 1.5 GHz and 1.75 GHz cavities inspired by ILC Blade tuner.

2022 ~ (R&D related to ILC):

- Development of optimized treatment recipe (High-Q/High-G R&D) for higher reliability in view of its industrialization for series cavity production and cost reduction
- Tuners: review and optimization of the INFN Blade tuner
- Areas of interest for Pre-lab: cavities, cryomodules, tuners (WP-1 & WP-2)

INFN LASA infrastructure: VT test stand and diagnostic for cavity qualification, cavity assembly and surface cleaning (HPR, UPW @ 18 M Ω cm, ISO4 clean room), RF power equipments and control electronics from 500 MHz to 3.9 GHz, cryogenics, etc.

SRF activities at INFN LASA: overview

- **Design**
 - Cavities
 - Cryomodules
 - Ancillaries
- **Qualification**
 - Cavities
 - SRF Ancillaries
- **Facilities**
 - RF Test Stand (50C)
 - ISO4-7 Clean Room (HPR, UPW, etc.)
 - Large Vertical Cryostat and advanced quench diagnostic
- **With Industry**
 - Fabrication of cavities and cryomodules
 - Mass Production of **European-XFEL** cavities and cryomodules (1.3 and 3.9 GHz)
 - **QA/QC**
 - **Technology transfer** (within XFEL contract)
 - Large Production of **ESS** Medium Beta Cavities
 - Upcoming Production of **PIP-II** LB650 Cavities

E-XFEL 3.9 GHz cryomodule & TESLA cryomodule evolution

INFN SRF cavity activities

ESS MB Cavity:
Example of EM
analyses performed:
Dipole HOM at

The EM design is transfer to mechanical analysis (loop) for estimating critical parameters as: Ring radius, Stiffness, Tuning sensitivity, Vacuum sensitivity, Lorentz Force Detuning, PED compliance

MECHAVITY
(new tool developed by INFN)

Mechanical Parameters	INFN design
Cavity wall thickness (mm)	4.2
Stiffening ring radius (mm)	70
Internal volume (l)	69
Cavity internal surface (m ²)	1.8
Stiffness (kN/mm)	1.7
Tuning sensitivity K_t (kHz/mm)	205
Vacuum sensitivity K_v	-8
LFD coefficient K_L	-1.8
$-k_{L0} = 21$ kN/mm (Hz/(MV/m) ²)	
$-k_{L2} = 21$ kN/mm (Hz/(MV/m) ²)	

PIP-II LB Cavity: Example of EM analyses performed: Dipole HOM at 1678 MHz showing partial reflections in the FPC

G. Ciotti, former student of INFN, working at TJNAF on EB-S cavities

MoU between INFN and TJNAF
for the Development of low β Superconducting Cavities for Proton Accelerators

From the EM-mechanical design to cavity production

- RF procedures from Nb sheets to cavity
- Define production cycle to guarantee final length and frequency
- Define appropriate treatment (BCP, EP, annealing)
- Mechanical and RF measurement and control plan

RF Measurements

ESS DB

EP & BCP systems

EBW visual inspection

- Test of defined scheme on prototypes and on series cavities
- 2 K test for final acceptance

ESS

XFEL 3.9 GHz

LASA VT stand:
bunker and
diagnostic

LASA cavity tuning machine: E-XFEL 3.9 GHz & ESS

XFEL 3.9 GHz

ESS

TRASCO

PIP-II

INFN cryomoules and ancillaries & tune

Module 1 Module 2 & Module 4+

- Cryomodule: TESLA -> XFEL -> ILC: design criteria**
- High filling factor:** maximize real estate gradient/cavity gradient
 - long cryomodules/cryo-units, short connection
 - Moderate cost per unit length:**
 - simple design based on reliable technologies
 - low static heat losses in operation
 - Effective cold mass alignment strategy:**
 - Room temperature preserved at cold
 - Effective/reproducible assembling procedure:**
 - Clean room assembly just for the cavity string
 - Minimize time consuming operations (cost/reliability)
- Cryomodule diagnostic tool: WirePositionMonitor (WPM)**

Tuners
Design, development and experimental qualification of tuners and control systems for many international projects

INFN large scale production: E-XFEL & ESS

Experience on large scale production of SRF cavities:

- Prototypes for debugging entire production cycle (detailed specs definition)
- Technology transfer to industries, infrastructure & process qualification
- Quality control (external) and experts support to industries
- Cavity performance analysis for fast feedback to industries

European XFEL (WP04 1.3 GHz cavity production DESY/INFN)

First example of large scale (800) cavity production at industry: a big success!

- 75%: OK first test (remaining recovered after retreatments), 1% rejected, rate: 8 cav/week

European XFEL (WP46) 3.9GHz cavities & cryomodule (+ spare)

INFN responsibility:

- **Cavities:** Nb materials, production from raw to ready for VT, cavity qualification (and recovery), QA/QC & document flow (INFN/industry/DESY)
- **Blade tuners & magnetic shield:** design and production (assembly)
- **Cryomodule:** design and production (assembly)

QA/QC & production cycle

ESS 704.4 MHz medium β cavities (36)

INFN responsibility: Nb materials, production from raw to ready for VT, cavity performance (and recovery), delivery to CEA for string assembly, QA/QC and documents flow between all partners

QA/QC & production cycle

704.4 MHz for ESS

INFN in view of ILC (Pre-lab): past & future activities

INFN blade-tuners developed to improve the ILC filling factor

CM2 equipped with Fermilab "short" cavities and INFN Blade tuners

Cryomodule assembling tools, developed by INFN-LASA for TESLA/XFEL and globally distributed for ILC and LCLS-II

Special 4 cavity Module and tuners for S1-Global at KEK

Areas of interest for Pre-lab:

•Cavities (WP-1)

- Development of optimized treatment recipe (High-Q/High-G R&D)
 - Cold EP
 - Mid Temperature baking (300 °C)
 - Rotational BCP
 - On-line thickness monitor during EP
- Series cavity industrialization and cost reduction

•Cryomodules and Tuners (WP-2)

- Cold mass and ancillaries
- Review and optimization of the INFN Blade tuner

Spain

Spanish Network on Future Colliders

Chairs: Marcel Vos (IFIC) & Alberto Ruiz (IFCA)

Active since 2005 (1-2 meetings/year)

Scope:

The main objective of this thematic Network is to coordinate the Spanish activities on physics studies and development of new technologies in view of future colliders for Particle Physics (mostly ILC & CLIC, now also FCC)

Includes: Accelerator, Theory, Experimental and Technological groups

Works/coordinates actions with industry: INDUCIENCIA platform and INEUSTAR association

Documents produced recently (May 2021):

1. Scientific and technological case of the ILC: Spanish Contribution (*signed by ~200 physicists, in English*)
2. Spanish industrial opportunities at the ILC (*in Spanish*)

Spanish technological/industrial interests to contribute to the ILC accelerator:

- **CIEMAT/IFIC:** contribution to the splittable, super-conducting magnets of the main LINAC (*both groups got funding for this project, period: 2021-2024*)
- **ALBA:** interest in the design of parts of the ILC damping ring
- **ESS-Bilbao:** interest expressed in the beam dump system of the ILC

Activity	# Groups
Accelerator	6
Si/Tracking	6
Si/Pixel	5
Calorimetry	3
Phenomenology	4

ALBA Contribution to Future Colliders

- EU H2020 Project EuroCirCol
 - WP4: FCC Cryogenic Beam Vacuum System

- Contract KE with CLIC-CERN:
 - WP1: Damping Ring Stripline Kicker tests
 - WP2: Collective Effects
 - WP3: Beam Instrumentation & Diagnostics
 - WP4: Damping Ring RF System

- Contract KE with FCC-CERN:
 - High Temperature Superconductors for the FCC Vacuum Screen

- EU H2020 - ARIES – ADA
 - WP8: Diagnostics for future accelerators

- Contract KE with FCC-CLIC-CERN:
 - Novel imaging diagnostics for future accelerators

ALBA, Synchrotron Light Source

F. Pérez

~2017:

- Contract KE with CLIC-CERN
- EU H2020 - ARIES – ADA

2018-2021

- EU H2020 Project EuroCirCol
- Contract KE with FCC-CERN
- Contract KE with FCC-CLIC-CERN

L. García-Tabarés

~2017:

Spanish Contributions to E-XFEL			
COMPONENT	TYPE	QUANTITY	CONTRIBUTOR
Superconducting Combined Magnets	SC Magnet	103	CIEMAT
Moving Tables (Movers)	Mechanics	101	CIEMAT
Electronic Control Racks	Electronics & Instrum.	101	CIEMAT
Superconducting Magnets Power Supplies	Electronics & Instrum.	240	CEI/UPM

- Contribution to IFMIF (2014-now):
 - ✓ Resistive magnet.
 - ✓ Superconducting magnet.
 - ✓ Scraper.
 - ✓ Buncher cavity
 - ✓ MEBT

2018-2021

- Prisma Project (2018-2023): A CIEMAT-CDTI Collaboration Program for Research on High Field Magnets, Supported by SGI/MCI & CERN.
- The splittable, conduction cooled superconducting magnets allocated in the Main Linac Cryomodules to focus and steer the beam for ILC (2021-2024).

Spanish contribution to CLIC			
COMPONENT/CONTRIBUTION	TYPE	QUANTITY	CONTRIBUTOR
Power Extraction Transfer Structures (PETS)	RF	12 (Partial)	CIEMAT
Double Length PETS for CLIC	RF	1	CIEMAT
Accelerating Structures	RF		CIEMAT
Longitudinally Variable Field Dipole	PM Magnet	TBD	CIEMAT
Kicker for CLIC Damping Ring	Special Magnet	1	IFIC & CIEMAT
BPM for CLIC Drive Beam	RF, Instrumentation	1	IFIC
Accelerating Structure Test Bench	RF, Instrumentation	1	IFIC
ALBA Contribution to CLIC Study	Several		ALBA

2007-now

Spanish Contribution to LHC-Hi Lumi			
COMPONENT	TYPE	QUANTITY	CONTRIBUTOR
Radiation Resistant SC Sextupole Corrector Magnet	SC Magnet	1	CIEMAT
Radiation Resistant SC Octupole Corrector Magnet	SC Magnet	1	CIEMAT
Participation in the LHC Long Shutdown	Manpower	8 man-year	CIEMAT
Development of a Nested Dipole	SC Magnet	1+2 Prototypes	CIEMAT
Participation in the QUAQO Project	SC Magnets	2 Prototypes	CIEMAT
Participation in the development of SC Links	SC Power Line	2 man-year	CIEMAT
Participation in the development of a VAR Compensator	Power Converters	2 man-year	CIEMAT
Participation in programs for SEY reduction	Materials	3 man-year	CIEMAT

2014-now

CIEMAT Contributions to the E-XFEL

Superconducting Combined Magnets

Power Supplies for Superconducting Combined Magnets
(Contribution provided by the UP Madrid)

Moving Tables

Control Electronics Racks

Phase Shifters

CIEMAT Contribution to CLIC

Power Extraction Transfer Structures (PETS) for CLIC

Type	TBL PET	Double Length PET
Op. Frequency	12 GHz	12 GHz
Length	4 x CLIC	2 x CLIC
Technology	Warm in Octants	Warm in Octants: Minitank, Integrated Couplers
Industrialization	YES: Partial Supplies by Industry	

CIEMAT Contribution to CLIC (3)

Accelerating Structure for CLIC

Type	Travelling Wave
Op. Frequency	12 GHz
Length	230 mm
Aperture	4.8-6.2 mm
Technology	26 Warm Discs
Peak Input Power	61,3 MW
Industrialization	YES: Partial Supplies by Industry

CIEMAT Contribution to LHC-HL (1)

Superconducting Magnets for LHC-HL (Superferric Correctors)

Sextupole

Octupole

Type	Sextupole	Octupole
Integrated Field	0.055 Tm	0.035 Tm
Physical Length	160 mm	160 mm
Op. Current	100 A	100 A
Technology	NbTi Superferric	NbTi Superferric Rad. Resistant
Industrialization	HI Lumi LHC Magnets will be based on this development	

CIEMAT Contribution to LHC-HL (2)

Superconducting Magnets for LHC HL (Nested Dipoles)

MCBX H&V Combined Corrector Dipole for the Inner Triplets

Type	Combined	Corrector Dipole
Integrated Field		2.5 Tm
Physical Length		1200 mm
Aperture		150 mm
Technology	Nested NbTi Coils @ 1.9K	
Industrialization	Yes (TBD)	

CIEMAT Contribution to IFMIF (2)

Medium Energy Beam Transport Line (MEBT):

- Compact transport line between RFQ and cryomodules
- Main components: Five combined magnets, two bunchers, beam scrapers and beam diagnostics.
- Fully designed by CIEMAT; manufactured by Spanish industry
- **MEBT sent to Rokkasho**

Integration Activities

MEBT

CIEMAT Contribution to IFMIF (1)

DEVICE	DESCRIPTION/TECHNOLOGY	
RESISTIVE MAGNET	13 Combined Magnets (1 Quadrupole + 1 Dipole) to be made at industry (ANTEC). Water cooled magnet, radiation resistant.	
SUPERCONDUCTING MAGNET	8 Combined superconducting magnets (2 Solenoids + 2 Dipoles). NbTi wet impregnated magnets to be manufactured at industry.	
SCRAPER	2 Collimation Scrapers fabricated at industry (AVS). Water cooled. Driven by step motors in close loop.	
BUNCHER CAVITY	2 RF Buncher cavities @175 MHz made at industry (DPM). IH resonator with 4 acceleration gaps. Resistive Type. Water cooled.	

CIEMAT Contribution to High Field Magnets: The PRISMAC Program

PRISMAC: A CIEMAT-CDTI Collaboration Program for Research on High Field Magnets, Supported by SGI/MCI & CERN

HL-LHC MCBXF Magnets In-Kind Contribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training & Support on magnets and facilities • Use of Facilities during the set-up of CIEMAT Laboratory • Qualification of CIEMAT as a Technological Partner 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing a team, facilities and economical resources to all the activities • Prototype Development • Technology Transfer to Industry • Series Fabrication • Follow-up • Qualification of Industry as Industrial Partners • Management of IK contribution to CERN 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Funding • Industrial exploitation of the associated technologies (Early Alert) • Dissemination of the developed technologies to other fields (i.e. Space, Fusion, Light Sources, Energy..) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding the series production, components and new personnel • Supporting the Spanish Traineeship Program (FTEC) • Supporting the R&D Program on Key Technologies 	
Facility for very high field superconducting magnet prototypes					
Development of FCC model magnets					

The ILC Contribution

SCOPE OF CIEMAT CONTRIBUTION

The splittable, conduction cooled superconducting magnets allocated in the Main Linac Cryomodules to focus and steer the beam. The contribution includes the Magnet Power Supply and the Beam Position Monitor in collaboration with IFIC. CIEMAT has been very recently awarded with a 193.000€ grant from the Ministry of Science to afford the fabrication of the first magnet coils based on MgB_2 and Nb_3Sn technologies

	<u>ILC Cryomodule Magnet</u>		<u>E-XFEL Cryomodule Magnet</u>	
Type: Combined	QUADRUPOLE	DIPOLE (2 H&V)	QUADRUPOLE	DIPOLE (2 H&V)
Overall N° of Magnets	<315	<630	103	206
Integrated Field	36 T	0.075 Tm	5.97 T	0.00075 Tm
Peak Field	3.3 T		2,48 T	1.59 T
Magnetic Length	680 mm		169.6 mm	203.7 mm
Inner Diameter	78 mm		94.4 mm	83.6 mm
Op. Current	100 A		50 A	
Baseline Technology	<u>Splittable NbTi</u> Conduction Cooled		<u>NbTi</u> , He Bath Cooled in Vacuum Vessel	
Alternative Technology	<u>Splittable MgB₂</u> Conduction Cooled			

ESS Bilbao Contribution to ESS Accelerator: Activities

MEBT Designed, built and assembly.

MEBT Systems hardware testing and commissioning.

QUALITY CERTIFIED
ISO 9001
ISO 3834
ISO 45001
ISO 8100

Fast Kicker & RF design and testing.

Magnets Designed, built test and assembly.

RF Beam optics Thermomechanical Optimization

MEBT BUNCHER high power RF conditioning

ESS Bilbao Contribution to ESS Target

- ESS is driven by a 5 MW Spallation Target, this element is an ESS Bilbao in kind contribution (design, manufacturing and testing)
- The Target Wheel is composed by ~ 7000 W bricks assembled in a Stainless-steel vessel and cooled by helium. The wheel will be driven by a ~ 7 m long coaxial pipe (Target Shaft)

Target Wheel

Drive Unit

Target Shaft

ESS Bilbao Contribution to ESS Target

- ESS Bilbao also contributes with additional equipment. ESS responsibilities includes from the conceptual design to the final testing:
 - Tuning Beam Dump (13 kW copper dump)
 - Monolith Vessel (Ø6 m x 8 m) Stainless steel vacuum vessel.
 - Proton beam window

Connection Ring

Lower and medium vessel

Tuning beam
SAT in Lund, January 2020
EAT test, November 2019

I. Bustinduy, M. Pérez

~2017:

- Contribution to ESS accelerator:
 - ✓ Fast Kicker & RF design and testing.
 - ✓ MEBT design, construction and assembly.
 - ✓ MEBT diagnostics and full integration.
 - ✓ Fast kicker and RF design and testing.
 - ✓ Beam optics and thermomechanical optimization.

2018-2021

- Contribution to ESS target:
 - ✓ 5 MW Spallation Target in kind contribution (design, manufacturing and testing)
 - ✓ Target Wheel (composed by ~ 7000 W bricks assembled in a Stainless-steel vessel and cooled by helium)
 - ✓ Tuning Beam Dump (13 kW copper dump)
 - ✓ Monolith Vessel (Ø6 m x 8 m) Stainless steel vacuum vessel.
 - ✓ Proton beam window

IFIC Accelerators R&D activities ~2018

4-OTRs for ATF2 for beam size and emittance measurements

Stripline kickers for beam injection and extraction in future linear colliders

Inductive Beam Position Monitors for CTF3

Conditioning tests of CLIC high-gradient prototypes

Vertical collimator for ATF2

Stripline BPM development for the CLIC drive beam

D. Esperante, N. Fuster, B. Gimeno

~2017:

- 4 optical tranOptics Design and Beam Instrumentation studies for the Beam Delivery System of Future Linear Colliders.
- Collimation system studies for Future Linear Colliders (CLIC).
- Beam halo collimation and wakefield studies at ATF2. Design, construction and installation of a vertical collimator in ATF2.
- Beam Dynamic studies for the EXT line of ATF-ATF2.
- High-gradient RF structures studies.
- Design and construction of Beam instrumentationsition radiation monitors for ATF-ATF2.
 - ✓ Inductive Beam Position Monitors for CTF3.
 - ✓ Stripline BPM development for the CLIC drive beam.
 - ✓ Stripline kickers for beam injection and extraction for a future Linear Collider.

The IFIC high-gradient laboratory (2018-2021)

- High-gradient normal conducting RF cavities research activities at S-Band frequency (2.9985 GHz).
- Commissioned in June 2019.
- Currently conditioning a Backward Travelling Wave structure for medical applications designed with an accelerating gradient of 50 MV/m.

- High-gradient test stand.

- Conditioning process and breakdown phenomena studies.

2018-2021

- Construction and commissioning of the IFIC high-gradient RF laboratory.
- High-gradient RF accelerating structure theoretical and experimental studies.
- Beam Position Monitor of the splittable, conduction cooled superconducting magnets of ILC to focus and steer the beam (in collaboration with CIEMAT). Funding approved & quantity under negotiation with Ministry of Science (2022-2025).

UK

All UK particle physics groups involved/interested in ILC, many since LCs proposed in 1990s:

Institute	Accelerator					Detector			Physics
	BDS/MDI	DR	Beam dumps	e+ source	RF	Si tracker	Calorimetry	DAQ	
Birmingham	X					X	X		X
Bristol						X		X	X
Brunel								X	X
Cambridge							X		X
STFC – Daresbury Laboratory	X			X	X				
Durham IPPP									X
Edinburgh						X			X
Glasgow						X			X
Imperial College							X	X	X
Lancaster				X	X	X			X
Liverpool		X				X			X
Manchester	X				X	X			X
Open University						X			
Oxford	X	X			X	X		X	X
QMUL						X			X
STFC – RAL			X	X		X	X	X	X
RHUL	X							X	X
Sheffield						X			X
Southampton									X
Sussex							X	X	X
UCL	X						X	X	X
Warwick						X			X

2004-2013:

ILC project + TDR preparation,

\$27M invested in:

damping rings,

positron source,

beam delivery system,

RF systems,

beam dumps ...

11 institutes, 80 people (45 FTE),
 25 postdocs + 50 PhD students
 engaged

> 2013: ongoing system design/optimisation, CLIC, nanobeam production (**ATF/ATF2**): **\$19M**

> 2018: nanobeam stabilisation (feedback + control) at **ATF2**, CLIC permanent magnets ...

SCRF systems/facilities of direct relevance to ILC, including:

HL-LHC crab cavity cryomodule: \$13M

ESS, PIP-II, Nb cavity fabrication/test: \$14M

Superconducting RF Activities

ESS High Beta Cavities (2016 – 22)

Cavity	ESS
Frequency (MHz)	704.42
Cavity Beta	0.86
Gradient (MV/m)	19.9
Quality Factor Q ₀	>5 x 10 ⁹ (BCP)
Number of Cells	5
Cavity Length (m)	0.915
Number of Cavities	84 (+4)

PIP-II HB650 Cryomodules (2019 – 25)

Cavity	PIP-II
Frequency (MHz)	650
Cavity Beta	0.92
Gradient (MV/m)	19
Quality Factor Q ₀	3 x 10 ¹⁰ (N2 Doped)
Number of Cells	5
Cavity Length (m)	1.42
Number of Cavities	18 (+2)
Number of Cryomodules	3 (6-cavity)

SuRFLab Test Facility

Crab Cavity Activities

ILC TDR (2008)

Beam-pipe radius = 18mm
Cavity iris radius = 15mm
Equator Radius = 47.37mm

3.9 GHz Single-cell ILC Crab Cavities

Cavities limited in gradient to 1 MV/m (~40kV/cell) – shielding implications.

HL-LHC (2010 – 24)

First ever evaluation of crab cavities with a proton beam on SPS in 2018!

- A 2-cavity pre-series (RFD) CM design being developed and manufactured by STFC.
- STFC also providing 4 production (DQW) CMs for installation during LHC LS3.

Helical Undulator Activities

Science and
Technology
Facilities Council

- UK successfully designed, manufactured, assembled and tested a complete 4m long ILC superconducting helical undulator module.
- The magnetic performance exceeded the field level required by ILC by 30%.

- UK has continued to develop superconducting planar and helical undulators ever since
- Currently our focus is on helical undulator for X-ray free electron lasers – similar parameters to those required by ILC

- UK has also developed leadership in adjustable permanent magnet dipoles and quadrupoles of significant relevance to ILC

UK ILC Pre-lab interests

ILC Pre-Lab

ILC TPD WP #	Proposed UK activity
	TPD Technical system (see Annex 4)
1	Main linac and SCRF systems: cavity industrial-production readiness
3	Main linac and SCRF systems: crab cavity system
5	Positron source: undulator technology
6	Positron source: undulator photon target technology
12	Damping Ring: system design
13	Damping Ring: collective effects
15	Beam Delivery System: system design of final-focus beamline

Outline scope of work identified:

\$16M technical

(+ ~\$50M for setting up facility for series cavity/cryomodule production for ILC)

Reviewed internally by STFC March 2021,

on hold pending positive signal from Japan and discussions MEXT ↔ BEIS/STFC